

ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS, STRUCTURE AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN THE COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract

This article is comprehensive and talks about the main problems in the economy of the countries of the Central Asian region, the level of development and opportunities for the development of trade and economic relations.

The purpose of the study is to analyze the directions and opportunities for improving trade and economic relations between the countries of Central Asia.

Keywords: Central Asia, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, foreign trade, export, trade.

Introduction

Economically developed and secure Central Asia is the main goal for Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan pays strong attention to the development of foreign trade relations with the countries of Central Asia, because foreign trade is of great importance in the development of the national economy, creates additional new jobs, and improves the competitiveness of manufactured products. increases, and at the same time, new technologies are important for development. Trade and economic cooperation relations with Central Asian countries are also of strategic importance in the economy of Uzbekistan and have an important place in the foreign trade of all countries.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, - "The peoples of our region are bound by thousand-year ties of brotherhood and good neighborliness. The willingness and earnest pursuit of practical cooperation, as well as the feeling of responsibility for the common future of all Central Asian countries, is a solid foundation and guarantee of the sustainable development and prosperity of the region. Our main goal is to make Central Asia a stable, economically developed and highly developed region with our joint efforts" [1].

The study of the specific features of the development of foreign trade relations between Uzbekistan and the countries of Central Asia is of great importance in the development of international trade and economic relations of Uzbekistan and determines the relevance of the article.

Literature review

The trade and economic cooperation of the Central Asian countries has been effectively studied by regional scientists and other major foreign scientists.

Uriintuya Batsaikhan, Marek Dombrovsky analyze the history, geography and politics of the Central Asian countries, their trade-economic integration, the reforms carried out in the countries, and their socio-economic indicators.

As a result of the analysis, despite the fact that Central Asian countries are rich in natural resources, they still show the remnants of the socialist regime in economic and political directions.

The article is comprehensive and shows the political and economic situation of Central Asian countries. Analyzes the relations of the countries of the region

with international organizations and other countries, but does not pay attention to the mutual trade and economic cooperation of the Central Asian countries and their prospects [2].

In the research conducted by Liu Junxia [3] energy diplomacy in Central Asia is discussed. Access to external energy markets through international investment has become an important strategy to eliminate energy risk and optimize the distribution of energy resources. With its important geographical location and diverse rich energy resources, Central Asia has attracted the attention of the international community and has become a destination for attracting foreign investment. However, the risk of corruption is a major problem for foreign investors, particularly in the energy sector. The share of corruption in international investment arbitration with five countries of Central Asia as a respondent is up to 75% in the energy sector. In these circumstances, choosing Central Asia as a place to invest is a decision made after considering both the opportunities and the risks involved in creating resource-intensive investments. Against this background, this document is intended to exert political influence on public administration bodies, politicians and foreign investors. Amendments to bilateral investment agreements, creation of a legal framework for Central Asian countries, investment promotion measures, self-management and self-protection of investors, and strengthening of the system of investment guarantees are proposed.

Analysis and results

As a factor that had a positive effect on the export of countries:

1. It is possible to obtain an increase in the price of raw materials and fuel and energy products in the world market. Because it can be seen that the share of this type of products in the export of Central Asian countries is high.

2. The devaluation of the national currency, which was carried out several times after independence, had a positive effect on the development of the country's exports. This practice had a positive effect on the competitiveness of local producers in the foreign market.

3. The development of foreign trade had a positive effect on the development of the economy of the main trade partner countries of the region.

But there was an increase in inflation and a decrease in the value of the national currency against the

US dollar. This caused a decrease in the price competitiveness of local producers in the foreign and domestic markets. A number of other factors that negatively affect the region's participation in international trade should also be considered:

- the country's access to seaports is limited;
- small population of the region, as a result of which the market capacity is relatively small;
- distance from large economic centers and increased cost of delivering goods to markets. As a result of the limited participation of local manufacturers in large world markets, the size of enterprises does not expand. As a result, production capacities are not fully utilized, and the economic benefits of economies of scale are lost.

- lack of development of the economic infrastructure in the countries at the level of world standards, which serves to increase the level of international trade efficiency.

The structural analysis of foreign trade clearly shows the extent to which the above-mentioned factors have influenced the development of foreign trade of Central Asian countries. The share of goods and groups of goods in the foreign trade of countries, as well as studying the geography of partner countries, shows what should be paid attention to in the development of foreign trade.

The share of goods in the export composition of Uzbekistan is 80.1%, they are mainly precious metals (28.5% with silver), energy carriers and oil products (14.1%), textiles (9.1%). , food products (8.5%, most fruits and vegetables - 6.7%), non-ferrous metal and products made from it (5.3%) and chemical products and products (4.9%) is coming.

Diversification was observed in the dynamics of the export composition during the last three years. In particular, the share of precious metals and fruit and vegetable products increased by 1.5%, the share of energy carriers and petroleum products by 1.3%, ferrous metals and their products by 0.8%, services by 0.2%, and textile products by 0.1%. .

On the contrary, there was a decrease in the share of precious metals, fruit and vegetable products, and the share of energy carriers and petroleum products, due to a significant increase in the remaining commodity groups.

The largest share of Uzbekistan's imports was accounted for by machinery and equipment and their parts (43.8%), chemical products and articles made from them (13.2%), and services (10.0%). The analysis of the composition of imported goods and services in 2019 showed that compared to 2018, the share of imports of machinery and equipment and their parts increased from 36.1% to 43.8%, food products and chemical products and the share of imports decreased from 9.1% to 7.8% and from 15.3% to 13.2%. Among the products imported in large volumes, there are also products that can be localized in the country. One of the main factors affecting the growth of imports is the increase in the import of machinery and equipment, which is the main part of the investments made in the country, and its share in the total import reached 43.8% (increase in the share of imports in the last three years 7.7 % points).

The following products can be indicated as the most promising goods for regional trade [4]:

- Fruit and vegetable products;
- grain, flour, bread and confectionery products;
- meat and dairy products;
- other food products: drinks, vegetable oil, baby food;
- textile products;
- building materials;
- chemical industry products: chemical fertilizers, plastic products, household chemicals and hygiene products, pharmaceuticals;
- machines and equipment, vehicles;
- minerals and primary products derived from them: hydrocarbons, metals;
- other products: tobacco and tobacco products, furniture, shoes, glassware, jewelry, glass and ceramics.

From the analysis of the commodity structure of the foreign trade of Central Asian countries, a number of general features can be distinguished:

- the share of mineral raw materials, fuel and energy resources in the export of countries is very high, and they specialize in these products;
- the share of finished and semi-finished products in the export of countries is small, and in some countries their share is increasing;
- countries have a high share of machinery, equipment and vehicles, and components in the import structure, and their increase is also related to foreign investments;
- the share of chemical and chemical industry products, metals and products made from metals remains high in the country's imports.

As noted, the high share of raw materials and semi-finished products in the exports of Central Asian countries causes a number of negative consequences for the socio-economic development of the countries.

First, the degree of dependence of the prices of the main export goods (oil, metals and cotton) of the Central Asian countries on the demand changes in the world market undermines the stability of export earnings. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the formation of the state budget and the stability of economic development.

Fluctuations in raw material products and prices affect the exchange value of the national currency. An increase in the price of raw material goods leads to an increase in the relative value of the national currency. This causes the level of competitiveness of other industries to decrease in the foreign market.

The amount of added value in the price of raw material products is less compared to finished and semi-finished products. As a result, in order to increase the volume of income, it is necessary to develop the production of products with high added value and to expand the export of these goods.

The directions of development of foreign trade relations in Central Asian countries are as follows [5]:

- attraction of foreign investments;
- establishing joint ventures and thereby creating new jobs for residents of both countries;

- establishing strategic cooperation and achieving regional economic freedom;
- sale of products in the single regional market and purchase of cheap products;
- exemption and removal from customs duties and fees;
- achieving competitiveness in the domestic market.

There are political and economic problems that hinder the development of trade and economic relations in the region, without solving them, the countries of the region cannot improve trade and economic relations. In particular: influencing factors are divided into 2 groups: internal and external factors.

The internal factors affecting the development of foreign trade relations of Central Asian countries are as follows [6]:

- policy of foreign economic activity carried out in the country;
- opportunities created in the country for foreign economic activity and benefits provided;
- customs policy;
- establishment of free economic zones and their activities;
- investment environment and introduction of innovations;
- market composition and size;
- introduction of new techniques and technologies, scientific innovations;
- geographical location.

External factors affecting the development of foreign trade relations of Central Asian countries are as follows:

- Unsolved problems of enclave regions in Central Asia;
- Transboundary rivers;
- differences in the level of development of Central Asian countries;
- Non-uniformity of membership and mutual relations in international organizations and integrations.

Conclusion and recommendations

The following general conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of the geographical composition of the foreign trade of Central Asian countries:

- geographical composition of the country's exports, depending on the level of processing of goods and products, they are sold to far abroad or CIS countries. Export of raw materials and fuel and energy products is carried out mainly to far foreign countries;
- It was found that the share of China and Russia in the foreign trade of the Central Asian countries is high and the difference in the share of the countries is large;

□ it can be seen that the share of the Republic of Korea, Turkey, Switzerland and Germany in the foreign trade of the countries is high

- Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have a significant share in the foreign trade turnover of the countries;
- the analysis of the geographical structure of the foreign trade of the countries shows that the mutual trade relations between the countries of Central Asia are developing in recent years.

Despite the fact that the composition of export and import products of the Central Asian countries is the same, after 2016, we will be able to see that the mutual trade turnover of the Central Asian countries is increasing and their share in the total trade turnover is increasing. This is certainly a positive trend and increases the opportunities for integration in the era of globalization.

In conclusion, it is necessary to conduct the correct foreign trade policy and implement reforms to optimize the structure of foreign trade.

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